

Mangoldt Graphs and Codes

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ABSTRACT: Binary codes from graphs have been studied widely since 1960's. Different graphs were widely used to construct codes with desirable properties. Here we introduce a new binary code the vertex code C from a given Mangoldt graph M_n , depending on the degree of the vertices of G . Next, we construct Mangoldt graphs using given vertex codes in such a way that the vertex polynomial of M_n is same as the weight enumerator of C .

Key words: Graph, Mangoldt graph, vertex degree, Vertex code, binary code.

I. INTRODUCTION

The arithmetic graphs associated with certain number theoretic arithmetic functions like the Euler totient function $\Phi(n)$, the divison function $d(n)$, the quadratic residue function and the Mangoldt function $\Lambda(n)$, for $n \geq 1$, an integer. The Mangoldt graph is named after German mathematician Hans von Mangoldt (1854-1925), who introduced the Mangoldt function $\Lambda(n)$ in 1897. These arithmetic graphs have been studied in detail by Madhavi (2003). Maheswari and Madhavi (2008) have studied the basic properties and vertex cover of the Mangoldt graph associated with Mangoldt function $\Lambda(n)$. In recent years Graphs and Codes studied by N. Suresh Babu et.al [6]. For coding concepts we refer to [8].

II. Preliminaries

- **Graph:** A graph G is an ordered pair (V, E) consisting of a finite set V of elements called **vertices** and a set E of unordered pairs of elements of V called **edges**, edges are well defined with respect to a relation on the vertex set. This graph is denoted by G or simply (V, E) .
- **vertex degree:** The **degree** of a vertex u in the graph G is the number of edges incident to u in G and is denoted by $\deg(u)$.
- The **minimum** and **maximum** of degrees of all the vertices in the graph G are called the minimum and maximum degrees of G and are denoted by $\delta(G)$ and $\Delta(G)$ respectively.
- **Mangoldt Function:**

Let $n \geq 1$ be an integer. The Mangoldt function $\Lambda(n)$ is defined as follows:

$$\Lambda(n) = \begin{cases} \log p & , \text{if } n = p^m, \text{ for some prime } p \text{ and some } m \geq 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

The following is the table of the values of $\Lambda(n)$ for $n = 1, 2, \dots, 10$.

n :	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
$\Lambda(n)$:	0	\log_2	\log_3	\log_2	\log_5	0	\log_7	\log_2	\log_3	0

- **Mangoldt Graph:** Mangoldt graph is defined as the graph whose vertices are the elements of the set $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and two distinct vertices x, y are adjacent if and only if $\Lambda(x \cdot y) = 0$ or $x \cdot y$ is not a power of a prime.
- **vertex code C_{M_n} :** The **vertex code** C_{M_n} of a Mangoldt graph M_n of order p is a collection of p code words having block length n , as minimum as possible and satisfying the distance condition, for every pair of adjacent vertices u_i and u_j of M_n , there corresponds code words c_i, c_j having the property,

$$d_H(c_i, c_j) = \begin{cases} |d(u_i) - d(u_j)|, & \text{if } d(u_i) \neq d(u_j) \\ 2, & \text{if } d(u_i) = d(u_j) \end{cases}$$

This distance condition is here after termed as **distance - degree criteria of Mangoldt graph**.

- A binary block code C of length n is a collection of binary words of length n . A word is a sequence of binary digits. In a binary word the only digits are 0 and 1. The size of C denoted as $|C|$ is the number of words of C .

III. Main Section

Codes from Mangoldt Graphs: A non linear code C can be constructed from certain classes of Mangoldt graphs such that to every vertex u_i , of the given Mangoldt graph M_n there corresponds a code word c_i of C satisfying:

- $\deg(u_i) = wt_H(c_i)$
- every pair of adjacent vertices u_i and u_j of M_n , there corresponds code words c_i, c_j having the property,

$$d_H(c_i, c_j) = \begin{cases} |d(u_i) - d(u_j)|, & \text{if } d(u_i) \neq d(u_j) \\ 2, & \text{if } d(u_i) = d(u_j) \end{cases}$$

- The block length n of C is chosen to be the minimum satisfying $\binom{n}{i} \geq$ number of vertices of degree j in M_n ; $\delta(G) \leq j \leq \Delta(G)$.
- The size of C is equal to the order of M_n .

The code so formed gives an idea about the number of vertices and the vertex degrees of the Mangoldt graph M_n and hence called vertex code of M_n .

3.1 Construction of Codes

Let M_n is a Mangoldt graph of order p , then to each vertex u_i of M_n , there corresponds a code word c_i of C such that $wt_H(c_i) = d(u_i)$. Then for a particular M_n any code C can be found with varying code lengths. Since most of the coding terminologies are defined on block codes we also aim to construct a block code C from the Mangoldt graph M_n . Since C should be of minimum block length n , if there are α_i vertices of degree i in M_n , $\binom{n}{i} \geq \alpha_i, \delta(M_n) \leq i \leq \Delta(M_n)$ in the size of the code C is $|C| = p$, the order of Mangoldt graph M_n .

Example3.2

Consider the Mangoldt graph M_6 in Figure 3.1

Figure 3.1

The vertex set of M_6 , $V(M_6) = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6\}$.

The block length of the required code C_{M_6} is 5, (since the block length is as minimum as possible) and the code words $c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5, c_6$ corresponding to the vertices $u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6$ can be chosen respectively as 10000, 11100, 11110, 11010, 11010, 11101, 11111.

Note 3.3: For every pair of adjacent vertices with same degrees and to the other vertices adjacent to these vertices, corresponding code words differ without any conditions.

Consider the vertices v_3 and v_5 which are adjacent and having vertex degree 4, and the adjacent vertices v_2 and v_4 having vertex degree 3. Both the pair are

adjacent to v_6 . Consider their corresponding code words,

$$\begin{array}{l} c_3 = 11110 \quad c_5 = 11101 \\ c_2 = 11100 \quad c_4 = 11010 \quad \text{and } C_6 = 11111 \end{array}$$

It can be viewed that,

$$\begin{array}{ll} (c_3, c_6) = 1 & (c_5, c_6) = 1 \\ (c_2, c_6) = 2 & (c_4, c_6) = 2 \\ (c_3, c_5) = 2 & d_H(c_2, c_4) = 2 \end{array}$$

And also considering the code words to the vertices v_1 adjacent to the vertex v_6 , we get,

$$(c_1, c_6) = 4$$

Thus we impose one more restriction in the construction of the codes from Mangoldt graphs (to standardize the codes from Mangoldt graphs and to study their nature), for the degree of the vertices and the distance between corresponding codes, if they considered are adjacent. So that, to every pair of adjacent vertices u_i and u_j of M_6 , there corresponds code words c_i, c_j having the property.

$$d_H(c_i, c_j) = \begin{cases} |d(u_i) - d(u_j)|, & \text{if } d(u_i) \neq d(u_j) \\ 2, & \text{if } d(u_i) = d(u_j) \end{cases}$$

Hence the new code C_1 for figure 2.1, is

$$C_1 = \{01000, 01110, 01111, 00111, 11101, 11111\}$$

The code so formed gives an idea about the number of vertices and the vertex degrees of the Mangoldt graph M_n and hence called vertex code of M_n .

Remark 3.4: Since M_n is a Mangoldt graph of order p , no vertex in M_n can have degree greater than $(p - 1)$, also at least two vertices will have same degree.

- All Mangoldt graphs need not have a vertex code.
- Next we give an algorithm to check the existence of the vertex code $C M_n$ of a Mangoldt graph M_n of order p .

3.5 Algorithm to check the existence of the vertex code C of a graph M_n of order p .

Step 1: Write the degree sequence of M_n and let α_i be the number of vertices with degree i .

Step 2: Fix the block length n of code C_{M_n} to be the minimum n satisfying $\binom{n}{i} \geq \alpha_i$ for every α_i .

Step 3: Start from a vertex v_k with maximum degree, assign a code word c_k arbitrarily to v_k , with length n as on Step 2 and $wt_H(c_k) = d(v_k)$.

Step 4: If more than one vertex has maximum degree, choose the first vertex arbitrarily, and assign a code word with weight equal to its degree. Next, the vertex is arbitrarily chosen and assigned a code word as earlier. Continue this process till all the vertices with a maximum degree are assigned code words.

Step 5: Next, a higher degree vertex is selected and code word of length n and Hamming weight equal to the degree of vertex is assigned to it, satisfying the distance-degree criteria with the code words assigned in Step 3 and Step 4.

Step 6. A vertex v_j having degree just one less than the maximum degree can be assigned a code word c_j only if v_j is adjacent to at most two vertices say v_k and v_l of maximum degree. Also if there exist any other vertex such that $(v_j) = (v_f)$ and v_f is also adjacent to v_k and v_l , then no distinct code words c_j and c_f can be assigned to the vertices v_j and v_f , then go to Step 9 and if no such v_f exists go to Step 7.

Step 7. Choose the next highest vertex degree and assign code words as in Step 5.

Step 8. Repeat Step 5 to Step 7 until code we reach Step 9 or Step 10.

Step 9. No vertex code of M_n exists.

Step 10. Code word for every vertex of M_n is obtained.

The code words for all vertices of M_n makes the vertex code C_{M_n} of M_n , such that

$$|C_{M_n}| = p.$$

Note. The vertex code of a Mangoldt graph is not unique.

3.6 To find the vertex code of given Mangoldt graphs using the algorithm

Here we apply steps 1 \rightarrow 10 of the algorithm 2.1.6, to find the vertex code of arbitrarily drawn graphs. Example 2.1.8 shows the existence of the vertex code of the drawn graph and example 2.1.9 and 2.1.10 show that the nonexistence of the vertex code.

Example 3.2

Consider Figure 3.2

Figure 3.2

The degree sequence is 6, 5, 5, 5, 4, 4, 1 ; $\alpha_6 = 1, \alpha_5 = 3, \alpha_4 = 2, \alpha_1 = 1$

The block length $n = 6$, which is the minimum satisfying $\binom{n}{6} \geq 1, \binom{n}{5} \geq 3, \binom{n}{4} \geq 2, \binom{n}{1} \geq 1$.

The maximum degree (6) vertex v_6 is assigned code words c_6 of the length 6 and the Hamming weight is 6.

Let $c_6 = 111111$

The vertices with then the maximum degree (5) are, v_3, v_5 , and v_7 all are adjacent to v_6 . So it is given a preference over v_3, v_5 , and v_7 and assigned a code word c_3, c_5 and c_7 , such that,

$$d_H(c_3, c_6) = d_H(c_5, c_6) = d_H(c_7, c_6) = 1 \text{ and}$$

$$\text{Hence } c_3 = 111110, c_5 = 111101 \text{ and } c_7 = 110111$$

$$\text{By distance degree criteria } d_H(c_3, c_5) = d_H(c_3, c_7) = d_H(c_5, c_7) = 2$$

Now the vertices, v_2, v_4 have degree 4 and all have equal priority in getting assigned a codeword. So choosing randomly and assigning code words c_2, c_4 respectively to the vertices, v_2, v_4 only

$$d_H(c_2, c_6) = d_H(c_4, c_6) = 2$$

$$\text{Hence } c_2 = 111100, c_4 = 111001$$

$$\text{By distance degree criteria, } d_H(c_2, c_4) = 2$$

And finally only one vertex v_1 is assigned a codeword c_1 it is adjacent to v_6 .

$$\text{Then } d_H(c_1, c_6) = 5$$

$$\text{Thus the vertex code } c_1 = 100000$$

The vertex code of C of C_{M_7} is:

$$C = \{100000, 111100, 111110, 111001, 111101, 111111, 110111\}$$

3.7 To show the non- existence of the vertex codes of Mangoldt graphs M_{10} (Fig 3.3) and M_{11} (Fig 3.4).

Case 1: The Mangoldt graph M_{10} is shown in Fig 3

Fig 3.3

- Following the algorithm, the block length n of the required code C can be fixed as $n = 10$. Here, the vertices v_6 & v_{10} have the maximum degree 9. The vertices having degree next to the maximum degree are v_5 & v_7 (of degree 8).
- v_6, v_{10} are assigned as code words c_6, c_{10} of length 10 and Hamming weight 9 so that $c_6 = 1111111110, c_{10} = 1111111101$
- Here we cannot find the code words c_5, c_7 such that

$$d_H(c_6, c_5) = d_H(c_{10}, c_5) = 1$$

$$d_H(c_6, c_7) = d_H(c_{10}, c_7) = 1$$

Thus M_{10} is not vertex coded.

Case 2:

Figure 4, shows the Mangoldt graph M_{11}

Fig 3.4

- The degree of sequence is 10,10,9,9,9,8,8,7,7,7,2.
- $\alpha_{10} = 2, \alpha_9 = 3, \alpha_8 = 2, \alpha_7 = 3, \alpha_2 = 1$
- Block length n is chosen to be the minimum satisfying all $\binom{n}{10} \geq 2, \binom{n}{9} \geq 3, \binom{n}{8} \geq 2, \binom{n}{7} \geq 3, \binom{n}{2} \geq 1$ where $n = 11$.
- The vertices v_6 and v_{10} with maximum degree are arbitrarily assigned two code words c_6 and c_{10} with length 11 and Hamming weight 10, where $c_6 = 11111111110, c_{10} = 11111111101$
- The vertices v_5 and v_7 with maximum degree are arbitrarily assigned two code words c_5 and c_7 with length 11 and Hamming weight 9, also they should satisfy,

$$d_H(c_6, c_5) = d_H(c_{10}, c_5) = 1$$

$$d_H(c_6, c_7) = d_H(c_{10}, c_7) = 1$$

Since, there exists only one codeword 11111111100 satisfying these conditions either v_5 or v_7 can be assigned as a code word.

- Thus the vertex coding of Mangoldt graph M_{11} ends in failure.

Result: Let M_n be a Mangoldt graph having vertex code C_{M_n} . Then the vertex polynomial of M_n is the same as that of the weight enumerator of C_{M_n} .

We have, for any given Mangoldt graph M_n , its vertex polynomial (2) of $S_{M_n}(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\Delta(M_n)} a_j x^j$, where a_j is the number of vertices with degree j .

Since our study is restricted only to connected graphs, $S_{M_n}(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{\Delta(M_n)} a_j x^j$.

In the vertex code, we define here the code words depend on the vertex degrees of the corresponding Mangoldt graphs. The Hamming weight of each code word equals the degree of the corresponding vertex.

Also in (2) the weight enumerator of a code C is defined as $W_c(x) = \sum_{k=1}^n c_k x^k$, where c_k denotes the number of code words with Hamming weight k .

In vertex code $\delta(M_n) \leq k \leq \Delta(M_n)$.

Thus $W_c(x) = S_{M_n}(x)$.

3.8 Construction of Mangoldt graph using given code:

To check whether the given code $C = \{c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots, c_n\}$ can be retraced to a Mangoldt graph M_n

1. If $|C| = n$ it is assumed that the Mangoldt graph M_n to be constructed from C is of order n .
2. Write the weight enumerator $w_c(x)$ of C , which in turn gives the vertex polynomial of M_n . Thus giving the number of vertices with particular degrees.
3. Write down the degree sequence.
4. Check whether the degree sequence is graphical.
5. If the degree sequence is graphical, evaluate, $d_H(c_i, c_j) \forall c_i, c_j \in C$.
6. If $d_H(c_i, c_j) = 2$ and $wt_H(c_i) = wt_H(c_j)$, then c_i and c_j may represent the code words of two adjacent vertices v_i and v_j having same degree of the Mangoldt graph.
7. Find the possibility of each code word to be a representation of the adjacent vertices in the required Mangoldt graph.
8. Every code word with weight m should be in degree - distance relation with at least m code words, if not no such Mangoldt graph M_n exists with given C as vertex code.
9. Try to draw the Mangoldt graph by plotting n vertices, the given n code words and join the vertices satisfying degree- distance relation.

3.9 To check the existence of Mangoldt graphs and its graph for a given code.

Example 3.10 :

Consider the code $C_1 = \{10000, 11010, 11110, 10011, 11011, 11111\}$.

From the given code C_1 , $W_{C_1}(x) = x^5 + 2x^4 + 2x^3 + x = S_{M_6}(x)$

$|C_1| = 6 = \text{Order of required Mangoldt graph} = M_6$

The degree sequence is 5,4,4,3,3,1.

Let the code C_1 can be written as $C_1 = \{c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5, c_6\}$ where,

$c_1 = 10000$ $c_2 = 11010$ $c_3 = 11110$

$c_4 = 10011$ $c_5 = 11011$ $c_6 = 11111$

We have $d_H(c_2, c_4) = 2 = d_H(c_3, c_5)$

Assign the vertex v_6 to code c_6 with degree 5 and reimagining vertices v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 and v_5 corresponding code words c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5 , each having the degrees are 1,3,4,3,4 respectively.

Here the pair of vertices v_2 and v_4 is not adjacent to each other. And the vertex v_1 is only adjacency to v_6 .

The vertex v_6 is adjacent to all other five vertices, then the Mangoldt graph M_6 from C_1 is shown in below

Fig.3.5

Fig 3.5

Example 3.11 :

Consider the code $C_2 = \{1000000, 1111000, 1111110, 1110100, 1111101, 1111111, 1111011, 1110010\}$.

From the given code C_2 , $W_2(x) = x^7 + 3x^6 + 3x^4 + x = S_{M_8}(x)$

$|C_2| = 8 = \text{Order of required Mangoldt graph} = M_8$.

The degree sequence is 7, 6, 6, 6, 4, 4, 4 and 1.

Let the code C_2 can be written as $C_2 = \{c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5, c_6, c_7, c_8\}$

where, $c_1 = 1000000$ $c_2 = 1111000$ $c_3 = 1111110$ $c_4 = 1110100$

$c_5 = 1111101$ $c_6 = 1111111$ $c_7 = 1111011$ $c_8 = 1110010$

We have $d_H(c_2, c_4) = d_H(c_2, c_8) = d_H(c_4, c_8) = d_H(c_3, c_5) = d_H(c_3, c_7) = d_H(c_5, c_7) = 2$

Assign the vertex v_6 to code c_6 with degree 7 and reimagining

vertices $v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7$ and v_8 corresponding code words $c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5, c_7, c_8$, each having the degrees are 1, 4, 6, 4, 6, 6, 8 respectively.

Choose highest weight of the given code is the vertex v_6 is adjacent to all other seven vertices.

And the vertex v_1 is only adjacency to v_6 .

Choose second highest weight of the given codes are the vertices v_3, v_5, v_7 is adjacent to all other vertices except v_3 . The required Mangoldt graph for the given code is shown in below

Fig.3.6

Fig 3.6

Conclusion

We construct vertex codes for Mangoldt graph M_n when $n=6,7,8,9$. For M_1 to M_5 graphs, vertex codes are not formed, since they are disconnected graphs are having isolated vertices. For $n \geq 10$, we cannot construct vertex codes for Mangoldt graph M_n . Next vertex codes of some Mangoldt graphs are constructed. Finally, we construct Mangoldt graph $M_n \forall n = 6, 7, 8, 9$ given vertex codes. For $n \geq 10$, we cannot construct the Mangoldt graphs using vertex codes.

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